
Journal of Tourism&Management Research

ISSN: 2149-6528

2021 Vol. 6, Issue.2

<http://ottomanjournal.com/index.html>

The Effect of Human Resources Practices on Employee Performance: The Mediating Role of Organisational Culture

Abstract

Employee performance remains one of the most effective tools used for the development, growth and productivity of services organisations. Management of such enterprises strengthens their human resources practices to develop a talented human capital. They are also putting tremendous efforts into creating the best organisational culture that leads to their workforce satisfaction and performance. This study aims to determine HR practices' effect on employee performance through the mediating role of organisational culture. Data collected from 400 hotel employees working in four and five stars hotels in Lebanon. Regression results indicate that human resource practices significantly associated with employee performance. Besides, hierarchical regression results revealed that organisational culture might partially mediate the relationship between HR practices and employee performance. Lebanon is recently putting into effect an employee-specific organisational culture. The results confirm that the critical variable that positively influences HR practices and employee performance is organisational culture.

Keywords: *Organisational culture, employee performance, HR practices, hotels, Lebanon*

Jel Codes: M10, M31, O14, M12

Submitted: 05.04.2021; **Accepted:** 31.07.2021

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ORIGINAL SCIENTIFIC PAPER

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2021, Vol.6, No.2, pp. 867-889. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6479188

1. Introduction

For decades, employee performance (EP) has received considerable attention in the literature and its core consideration for its success and competitiveness (Sutduean et al., 2019). EP can be identified and seen as the key driver of individual attitude, behaviour and performance (Khan & Wisner, 2019). Furthermore, EP positively affects the individual and organisational gains, financial growth, return on assets, profitability, employees' job performance and client satisfaction (AL-Qudah et al., 2014). In other words, employees are core and blood supply for the organisation due to their vital role and contributions to achieve the organisational goals (Demerouti & Cropanzano, 2010). EP is connected with the performance of an organisation. Successful organisations believe that HR practices are a vital indicator of how employees perform. In their study, Boselie et al. (2005) mentioned that human resource management (HRM) is considered as a set of employee management practices in 104 different research studies. Imperatori et al. (2020) defined HR department as a management of personnel and an organizational function that work on organizing HRM for the purpose of facing all the recent challenges. HRM is a systematic process and approach that operate through providing dimensions and practices that ensure supporting employees in their work life cycle starting from recruitment till exit (Sivathanu & Pillai, 2018). In the same context and to be more specific, HR practices are implemented in that complex work environment for covering staffing activities, searching and hiring talented personnel for the desired role. For the second stage HR practices provides all the adequate training activities for the purpose of preparing employees for their job position and collaborate technologies and practices to sustain personnel's high performance, such as performance appraisal system and knowledge management and reward systems (Prieto & Pérez-Santana, 2014). Moreover, HR practices are recognized as a substantial and fundamental part of the organization because they support organizational performance and shape a sustainable advantage based on highly skilled personnel (Margherita & Braccini, 2020).

Therefore, employee performance needs to be prioritised to upscale the organisational performance and achieve competitive advantage (Hassan, 2016). HRM practices are positively associated with employee behaviour (Huselid, 1995) and motivation (Delery & Roumpi, 2017). The systematic studies that linked HR practices and performance has been studied widely in the literature. It is agreed that there is a link between HR practices and employee performance (Arthur, 1994; Gerhart & Milkovich, 1992; Guest, 1997; Huselid, 1995; MacDuffie, 1995). Based on this background, a critical issue can be identified as enhancing employee performance at work. Therefore, this study analyses the role of employee performance and organisational culture and how they facilitate each other in the Lebanese hotel industry.

2. Literature Review

2.1 HRM in Hotel Industry of 21st Century

Hoque (2000) noticed that traditionally, the hotel industry has not been very appreciative of the HRM implementation. The study claimed that the industry remained mostly backward in its implementation of HR practices as it was applied primarily to enhance work-related outcomes rather than improving overall employee commitment. It was further elaborated that since the hotel industry is conventionally classified as a labour-intensive and exploitative industry, the role of HRM, mainly the strategic role, was overlooked.

In the 21st century, the hotel industry witnessed an immense transition, mainly due to technology advancement. The internet has created virtual marketplaces and reduced the void between service-provider and customers. Customers in the 21st century are better informed than their predecessors. The customers can now extract the full-service related information about different hotels at their homes' comfort and compare different providers' service quality on the internet. Hence, it compelled the hotel firms to improve their services and match the

quality standards with that of the competitors. It has become imperative for 21st-century firms to be transparent and fair in their operations (Burckhardt & Byberg, 2011; Henson, 2003). However, it does not mean that technology has advanced only to hotel firms' disadvantage.

The technology has improved firms' access to their customers, facilitated knowing the customers better and understanding their demands. The 21st century market is the "buyer market," i.e. the buyers rule the market. The 21st century's hotel customer is distinct, informed and connected. If they want to survive, the sellers need to understand and meet customers' expectations. Technology enables firms in the 21st century to quickly inform and promote their offerings to the target customers compared to past firms. The 21st century in the global hotel industry context can also be marked with a greater focus on total quality management. While quality management as a concept evolved in the previous century, the real emphasis on it has been laid in the 21st century (Burckhardt & Byberg, 2011 and Henson, 2003).

Huda et al. (2014) examined the role of HRM in recruiting 21st century hotel industry in the specific context of selected star rated residential hotels in Bangladesh. The study outlined the hospitality industry's economic significance by stating that it contributes significantly to nations worldwide' gross domestic product (GDP). The relevance of HRM for the country's hospitality industry was laid down based on recruitment, which is one of the best HR practices. It was argued that this is a service-oriented and labour-intensive industry; thus, having an efficient workforce is an absolute imperative for delivering quality services. The study described that the hospitality industry does not enjoy a good reputation in the Bangladeshi culture; hence it is challenging to get a talented workforce pool. Laying down the importance of HRM in today's hospitality industry.

Al Hrouf & Mohamed (2014) established the importance of HRM in the hospitality industry by stating that it is its competitiveness source. The study emphasised frontline employees' skill development in the hotel industry as they serve as the interface between the firm and the customers. Training and development and continuous performance appraisal are the HR practices which have been stressed under study. The study believes that HRM enhances hotel employees' competency and productivity, leading to enhanced customer satisfaction in present times. The study validates its point on globalisation, liberalisation and increased competition which compels hotel firms to effectively and efficiently employ their human resources to make a difference.

While HRM's role in skill development was outlined by Al Hrouf and Mohamed (2014), its role in tackling the high employee turnover in the hotel industry has been the subject matter of the research conducted by (Ezeudji & Mbane, 2017). With a growing focus on the quality, hyper-competitive marketplaces, and customer demands' dynamism, the pressure on the hotel industry employees is on the rise, which has worsened the industry's pervasive attrition problem. The utility of HRM concerning reducing employee turnover has been admitted in a recent study by (Ezeudji & Mbane, 2017), who conducted the study for hotels in Cape Town, South Africa. The study elaborated that the hotel industry worldwide is striving against employee turnover problems which cause costs, both financial and non-financial, like losing the customers' or delaying the services. The study conducted a survey of employees from sampled three, four and five-star hotels in Cape Town to explore the relationship between work conditions and employee retention. The study concluded that employee retention is positively influenced by multiple HR practices, such as employee career development, performance appraisal, work relationships, and employee engagement. The research specifically concluded that elaborated working schedules, employees' perception of unjustified compensation, and stringent supervision mechanisms are the leading factors that cause employee turnover in the hotel industry. The role of the HRM is thus apparent here.

Ažić (2017) proclaimed that in present times, the hotel industry could be characterised by the complexity of customer demands, thus compelling the HR managers to identify novel

ways to manage relationships with employees as well as the customers. The study also asserts that the modern hotel industry is very labour intensive involving many human interaction and interrelationships within the workplace. As such, employee satisfaction becomes highly critical for the hotel firm's overall well-being compared to other industries. The research concluded that a harmonious relationship with the supervisors and the co-workers' aids in employee engagement in the hotel industry and enhances employee performance. The research thus highlights the role of HRM in the modern hotel industry.

The section outlined that traditionally HRM has mostly remained an overlooked area, but it has become an indispensable part of the modern hotel industry as it adds to the firms' competitiveness, sustainability, and goodwill. The focus laid on the HRM to adopt the strategic role in the hotel industry of the 21st century.

2.2 Employee Performance

Employee performance as an essential concept to human resources and organisational development had different definitions in the literature. While a few scholars strictly restrict the term to task-related performance, others also include teamwork, behaviour towards the customers, training receptiveness, and task adaptability into the term's scope (Gremier, 2011; Kehoe and Wright, 2013; Mansour, 2021). Nevertheless, in simple terms, it denotes the efforts made by an individual member of the organisation towards achieving an assigned task (Pradhan & Jena, 2017). Several factors impact employee performance and many scholars have researched their inter-relationship with other organisational variables and outcomes. Luthans et al. (2008) and Peterson et al. (2009), through respective empirical studies, deduced that if employees have a positive mind frame (confidence, flexibility, optimism and worth), their performance is bound to be satisfactory, and such employees will exhibit higher employee commitment and satisfaction. While Luthans et al. (2008) explored the intrinsic factors, Walumbwa et al. (2011) examined the connection between upright leadership and performance with a sample of supervisors from China. They examined social exchange, social learning and social identity theories and found that ethical leadership, particularly, leadership-member exchange, certainly boosts the employee performance and organisational identification. From the perspective of the impact of employee performance on organisational performance, Sadikoglu and Zehir (2010) conducted an empirical study amongst Turkish firms. They found that employee performance and organisational innovation moderately negotiate the inter-connectivity of Total Quality Management (TQM) practices and organisational performance. Setyawaty et al. (2017) explored four factors: training and development opportunities, self-effectiveness, the organisation's culture, and organisational membership behaviour and found a positive as well as the significant impact of these factors on employee performance. They also expressed the need to study more factors like leadership style and workplace environment to impact an organisation's performance.

2.3 Organizational Culture

Organisational culture can be defined as the framework comprising the beliefs, values, and perspectives that guide an organisation's members' behaviours. The scope of the term 'organisational culture' is exhaustive as it can include an organisation's dress code, linguistic regulations, behaviour set, myths, norms, rituals, and assumptions (Bitsani, 2013; Leovaridis & Cismaru, 2016). However, Alisa and Senija (2010) points out that there is no single definition of organisational culture despite being a popular term among researchers. The term has often been used in management and organisational theory, so the existing literature views are divided. Alisa and Senija (2010) elaborate on the influence of organisational culture on an organisation proclaiming that it can have contrasting effects. It can either be a key to organisational success, but in other incidences, it can also be a 'silent killer.' If the organisational culture is positive and encourages the employees' efforts, it can contribute

significantly to organisational success. However, if the organisational culture is not well aligned to the organisational objectives, it can lead to its destruction. Corporate performance and organisational culture's relationship drew many scholars' attention. For instance, the study found a strong positive correlation between organisational culture and corporate performance. Ojo's study (2009) also asserted that organisational culture influences employees' work commitments and organisational goals. The author has recommended that organisations strive to improve the culture as it will ultimately improve organisational performance. The study also recommends that organisations help individual, organisational members align their values and beliefs to the organisational culture.

2.4 Relationship between HRM Practices and Employee Performance

The practices selected for this study are based on the hospitality industry's importance on employment creation and service effectiveness. As it is a labour -intensive industry, HR practises for the hospitality industry is crucial to analyse. However, the HR practices selected to be used in this study are defined and hypothesized as follows.

Selection and Recruitment – Organisations depend on recruitment and selection when it comes to their overall resourcing strategies—recognising and ensuring positions while recruiting people aids in the succession of short to medium-term positions (Elwood & James, 1996). The key strategy in recruiting and selecting employees is to recruit qualified people who would make the best candidates for the organisation's positions (Gamage, 2014).

Evidence has shown a positive and meaningful link between recruitment, selection and an enterprise's performance (Gamage, 2014). For Example, Sang (2005) found a helpful connection between recruitment, selection and business performance. The same positive results were seen in Ichniowski and Shaw (1999), Katou and Budhwar (2006) and Wright et al. (2005). Other studies, such as Syed and Jama (2012), prove that a successful recruitment and selection process is related to organisational performance.

Specific reference to recruitment and selection standards and organisational performance, Munyon et al. (2011) insisted that using advertisements, interviews, and other methods can ensure that the selected candidates effectively accomplish their new role. Huselid (1995) mentions that positive recruitment procedures aid in numerous applicants having set criteria to substantially influence the new employees' quality and skills. HR policies and practices are important forces shaping employee behaviour and attitudes. Hence, selection practice helps managers determine who will be hired for the right position (Gamage, 2014). If properly designed, the selection practice will identify candidates that withhold the skills to match the job; when a qualified person is selected for the job, efficiency rises. Literature such as Terpstra and Rozell (1993) stated an effective connection between recruiting, selection test validation and the use of formal procedures and firm profits. Similarly, Rauf (2007) found that recruitment and selection processes are positively related to organisations' performance. István (2010) observed many recruitments and hiring techniques based on objectivity, authenticity, cost, and usage scope.

In all, Sinha and Thaly (2013) noted that there are numerous recruitment approaches, and most organisations will use a combination of two or more of these as part of a recruitment process or provide their overall recruitment strategy. However, recruiting channels that should be used depend on the job position, its employer brand, its resources on its recruiting team, and how much recruiting budget the company has. Every recruiting network offers different benefits and limitations and works better for specific situations and companies. The best way to figure out what recruiting method works best for each company is to analyse metrics based on the past recruiting efforts, not everybody else's efforts. (Sinha & Thaly, 2013). Based on the literature, hypothesis 1 developed as follows:

Hypothesis 1: There is a relationship between selection and recruitment program with employee performance.

Training and Development – In the HRM literature, training and development acknowledged as a significant predictor of employee motivation and employee performance. Scholars have conceptualised training and development as the programs designed and sponsored by the organisations to improve the employees' task-related skills and abilities to handle service-related complex situations (Karatepe et al., 2007; Schlesinger & Heskett, 1991; Yang & Fu, 2009). Therefore, the organisation's higher-level training and development are expected to improve performance. Training is an organised approach that allows employees to acquire the skills needed to accomplish tasks with improved behaviour (Armstrong, 2006). Training and development both help in developing any organisation. Desler (2008) said that training is the method to develop skills in the employees required to perform the job. The majority of organisations considered training and development vital in human resources activity. Training can also improve the employee's performance by developing their knowledge and skills. It is also an endeavour to develop employees' performance by possessing additional competencies for their current jobs or the future (Jackson and Schuler, 2000).

Training can increase employees' efficiency and effectiveness to increase organisational performance (Cook & Hunsaker, 2001). Employees carry out extensive training programs to improve their performance to increase their competitive advantage (Brown, 2005). Therefore, it is essential to develop employee development training programs to achieve organisational goals (Dobson & Tosh, 1998). The desired change can be achieved in the employee's performance by providing them with proper training (Huselid, 1995). Therefore, hypothesis 2 is developed as follows:

Hypothesis 2: There is a relationship between training and development program with employee performance.

Rewards and Compensation – Compensation is an important HRM practice implemented by an organisation for motivating employees towards their works. Compensation provides monetary value to employees for their work. Compensation allows organisations to hire qualified and skilled employees, reward the performance, and encourage company loyalty by minimising employee turnover. Compensations may include Basic Pay, Overtime, Bonuses, Travel/ Accommodation, Allowance, Stock Options, Medical Allowance, Commissions, and Profit-Sharing.

A recent study done by Hay points out that 20 per cent of employees plan to change their current position in at least five years. Employee retention turnover has become a more noticeable aspect of organisational life. Putting retention compensation strategies into effect has shown significant growth over the last several years. A study done by Frye (2004) shows a positive relationship between compensation and organisation performance. Frye (2004) reported that compensation strategies play a major role in hiring and retaining a skilled workforce. Firms are using performance-based compensation to reward their employees (Collins & Clark, 2003). It is argued that performance-based compensation positively influences the employee's performance (Brown et al., 2003). Moreover, Huselid's (1995) study showed a significant relationship between compensations and employee performance.

An effective HRM strategy is to combine performance and compensation systems that develop employees' will to work effectively and efficiently (Wright, 2005). Teseema and Soeters's research (2006) indicated a significant correlation between employee performance and compensation. Employers must view compensation practices favourable light as

compensation practices heavily influence employee recruitment, turnover and productivity. Thus, this study conceptualises hypothesis 3 as follows:

Hypothesis 3: There is a relationship between Pay, Rewards and Compensation program with employee performance.

Performance Appraisal – Performance appraisal is an efficient assessment of employees' performance in their assigned tasks. The purpose of performance appraisal is to increase employee motivation and self-esteem. Sels et al. (2003) stated that performance evaluation increases employee productivity and increases organisational performance. Performance appraisal as crucial practices help individuals in the organisation to develop professional growth and enhance performances. Moreover, transparent performance evaluation motivates employees to achieve the organisational objectives (Singh, 2004). Wan et al. (2002) reported that merit-based performance appraisal increases employee motivation and commitment, significantly affecting organisational performance. The key to the organisation's success relates to employees' willingness to play extra-roles (Ahmad & Schroeder, 2003). Satisfied employees minimise turnover and absenteeism. Therefore, the study theorises hypothesis 4 as follows:

Hypothesis 4: There is a relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance.

Career Growth – Employee performance is crucial for a company because its success results from its employees' performance. Robbins (2002) pointed out that a person's performance is influenced by internal factors, for instance, motivation and capability, and employees' opportunity to develop his/her career provided by the organisation. Career development will trigger the employee to improve his/her capability, which will eventually affect his/her performance in working. (Armstrong, 2001). The same result was attained in Gachunga and Wamoto (2012) research, which also showed that developing a particular company's career would influence employee performance. Guidance and facilitation from superiors- monitoring and coaching- for career development will give employees the clarity of direction and lane of career. They will meet their expectations and goals, which will become an effective means of motivating them to show their best performance.

Dewi and Utama (2016) research supports the statement that career development substantially influences performance. It means that the proper career development system will increase employee performance. Patrick and Kumar (2011) also clarify that career development will influence organisational performance, affecting its effectiveness. Charity (2015) pointed out that career development substantially impacts employee performance in the banking sector. The researcher also mentioned that organisations should improve career development to increase employees' performance and minimise turnover rate.

Akmal's (2015) research also supports Charity's research (2015). It proves that career development has a major influence on employee performance because career development organised properly by a company will provide a positive atmosphere for its employees to achieve their expected careers by increasing their motivation. Based on the above explanation, this research proposed a hypothesis as follows:

Hypothesis 5: There is a relationship between Career growth programs with employee performance.

Employee Communication – Effective communication is understanding education, empowerment and respect. Effective communication gives people the information they need

to become educated and informed. When people know, they feel respected and empowered and are motivated to perform at their best productivity and performance level. According to Salako (2016), communication "Lifeblood" of an organisation where miscommunication causes cardiovascular damage in more than one organisation. Callaghan (2004) mentioned that communication is how people make an effort to share meanings. Thus, as Bateman and Snell (2002) stated, multiple channels may be necessary, such as virtual terms and emails are not enough to communicate effectively within the organisation. Managers should engage in using audio meetings, video conferencing, voice mail and face to face communication. Moreover, organisations should have regular face to face meetings and ensure attendance is being made at scheduled virtually meetings. Regular updates status and two- way exchanges via multiple channels. Based on the above explanation, this research proposed a hypothesis as follows:

Hypothesis 6: There is a relationship between employee communication and employee performance.

2.5 The Mediating Role of Organisational Culture

Organisational culture is explained as a shared set of characteristics such as beliefs, values, and behaviours by the organisations' members (Lawson & Ventriss, 1992) that may increase quality employee performance (Hann et al., 2007). Organisational culture incorporates dynamism, creativity and entrepreneurship to ensure its long-term success (Cameron & Quinn, 2006). Several studies (e.g., Albrecht, 2012; Rastegar & Aghayan, 2012) have zoomed in on the direct impact of organisational culture and found that organisational culture is positively related to employee performance, such as employee engagement, turnover intentions (Timms et al., 2015) and organisational success (Sorensen, 2002). Although prior studies focus on the relationship between qualifications and engagement (e.g., Karatepe & Demir, 2014; Karatepe, 2013), the possibility that the relationship can vary with a mediating variable has not been considered (Lee & Ok, 2016; Rich et al. (2010). Parker and Griffin (2011) suggested that low levels of circumstantial issues (i.e. HR practices) not necessarily always apply low levels of employee engagement because work environment factors such as organisational culture may buffer the relationship between experiences, e.g. HR practices and employee engagement. Scholars argue that a mediating variable may play an essential role in modifying the relationship (Emmerik et al., 2005; Cavana et al., 2001). Chen (2004) showed that organisational culture buffered the relationship between leadership style and performance. Authors have stated that leaders with an inventive style may help increase employees' positive attitudes. Previous studies (e.g., Lim, 1995; Ogbannan & Harris, 2000) have also shown that organisational culture is a combination of different factors present within an organisation, increasing employee engagement with its positive role in the psychological health of employees.

Existing research observed various types of cultures in different types of organisation. For instance, Wallach (1983) identified three types of cultures, i.e. bureaucratic, innovative and supportive culture. Bureaucratic culture is defined as the official rules that the employees follow to perform a task without freedom, while innovative culture encourages employees to become creative and effective risk-takers. Moreover, supportive organisational culture gives more emphasis on human aspects and personal relationships with trust and collaboration. Wallach suggests these three cultures to be independent.

As Dikkers et al. (2004) defined optimum organisational culture as a supportive culture, the present study focuses on the supportive organisational culture to examine the mediating role of culture on HRM-employee performance relationship. Besides, HR practices are positively related to employee performance (Al Hrouf & Mohamed, 2014), and organisational culture plays a significant role in employees' positive behaviour towards their performance

(Chen, 2004), it is expected that organisational culture may buffer the relationship between HR practices and employee performance. Therefore, hypothesis 7 has been developed as follows:

Hypothesis 7: Organizational culture mediates the relationship between HRM practices and employee performance.

Hypothesis7a: Organizational culture mediates the relationship between selection and recruitment and employee performance.

Hypothesis7b: Organizational culture mediates the relationship between training and development and employee performance.

Hypothesis7c: Organizational culture mediates the relationship between rewards and compensation and employee performance.

Hypothesis7d: Organizational culture mediates the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance.

Hypothesis7e: Organizational culture mediates the relationship between career growth and employee performance.

Hypothesis7f: Organizational culture mediates the relationship between employee communication and employee performance.

2.6 Proposed Research Model

According to the literature described in this study, researchers have asserted that six HR practices can be associated with employee performance. Moreover, organisational culture as a mediating variable positively affects the relationship between HR practices and EP. Figure 1 represents the framework of this research.

Figure 1. Conceptual Model

3. Methodology

The current study resorted to a quantitative research method that allowed generalisation of the research's facts. Since the research population included all the hotels in Lebanon, the study's

scope is extensive. Therefore, it was neither practical nor possible to conduct the qualitative study, which offers an in-depth insight into the research problem but does not allow generalisations like quantitative study design. The research is conclusive, which resorted to deductive reasoning. This approach supported the testing of hypothesis.

3.1 Sampling and Data Collection

The population in case of the current study comprises the hotel industry in Lebanon, those having formal Human Resource Management (HRM) practices in place and thus allows studying the impact of HRM on the employee performance. Since Lebanon's hotel industry is vast, it was not practical to investigate the entire industry. Therefore, the researcher resorted to sampling due to the resource constraints and primarily to research within a specified time frame.

Study data were collected by using a random sampling technique. A self-administered questionnaire was used for data collection. The hotels of Lebanon were first categorised based on their ratings. The hotels which enjoyed the rating of four stars and five stars were included in the study. The reason for this inclusion was the judgment by the researcher that 4 and 5 stars rated hotels had a greater chance of having formal HR practices in place. Therefore, selecting employees from these hotels was based upon providing the necessary information that the researcher would require. The researcher first approached the list of Lebanese 4-star and 5-star hotels and then sorted 50 hotels out of them based on convenience. The HR managers of the selected 50 hotels were approached through mail which was acquired through their social media accounts, personal visits, or through acquaintances, as the case may be. The HR managers were informed about the study's purpose. Out of the selected 50, depending on the HR managers' convenience and level of interest, the researcher selected 40 hotels to be included in the study.

Data were analysed to identify, describe, and explore the relationship between HR practices and the employees' performance taking Lebanon's organisational culture as a mediating variable. Data were obtained from self-administered questionnaires completed by 400 respondents (n=400). The questionnaire was sent across to 10 different Hotels employees in Lebanon, wherein 40 respondents from each 10 of the hotels were administered. The data were analysed through correlation and regression analyses.

The closed-ended structured questionnaire prepared for the study was then shared with the HR managers of the selected 40 hotels, and they were further requested to provide access to the department-wise records of employees, which also contain their details like name, age, gender, and experience with the firm. The researcher noted down the email addresses of 12 employees who could best answer the questionnaire.

The respondents were chosen depending on the researcher's judgment and the respondents' different experiences. The questionnaires were then mailed to these 12 respondents from each of the selected 40 hotels, i.e., a total of 480 respondents. The respondents were requested to fill and email the questionnaires back within two weeks. The questionnaires were then sorted out, and ten questionnaires from every hotel were finally included for the analyses, which were the best according to the researcher's judgment. Considering this recommendation, the researcher selected the sample of 400 respondents from 40 hotels across Lebanon which enjoy the rating of 4 stars and five stars. The Lebanese ministry of tourism offers the classification criteria for hotels in the country, which is valid for two years; the same has been utilised to consider the hotels under study. Ten employees from each of the 40 hotels have been included in the primary survey study.

3.3 Research Instrument

The survey instruments were back-translated from English into Arabic by a certified translation service company. Responses to the items based on a 5-point scale option varied from 1= strongly disagree to 5= strongly agree. The questionnaire was divided into five sections. The first section was made to inquire about the respondents' demographic details, where four control questions were designed to describe the organisation's characteristics and its employees, such as gender, age, education qualification, and length of employment.

The second part included questions on their general background. The third section entailed questions relating to the Human Resource Management (HRM) practices based upon the Human Resource-Best Practices Scale (HR-BPS) developed by Ahmed et al. (2011). The scale contained twenty-nine items which required the respondents to respond on the five-point Likert scale (Abbas & Ahmed, 2014). Three items to measure selection and recruitment; five items for training and development; nine items for rewards and compensation; six items for performance appraisal; three items for career growth; three items for employee communication. The fourth and fifth sections of the questionnaire also contained statements that the respondents needed to respond on a five-point Likert scale. The fourth section contained statements about organisational culture's perception, where seven items were adopted (Al-Qudah et al., 2014). The fifth section comprised four items adapted from (Pradhan & Jena, 2017) related to employee performance measurement.

3.4 Statistical Analysis

The fundamental inferential and descriptive analysis was done using the software SPSS Version 23. For the descriptive analysis of the demographic profile, frequency distribution was applied. Cronbach alphas and factor loads were checked. Further, bivariate correlation and multiple regression were applied to analyses the effect of HRM on employee performance, with organisational culture as a mediating variable. Pearson correlation coefficient indicates the significance, direction, strength and significance of the bivariate relationship among all the variables measured at an interval or ratio level (Sekaran & Bougie, 2010).

Since the study aimed to see the effect of HR practices (cause or independent variable) on employee performance (effect/outcome or dependent variable), keeping organisational culture as a control variable, bivariate correlation helped identify the strength between the independent, and dependent variables. Once the relationship between the three variables was established, multiple regression was performed to understand the impact of independent variables and control variable on the dependent variable.

4. Results

4.1. Descriptive Statistics

As per the descriptive findings presented in Figure 2, 61% of the respondents were male employees, and 39% were female. Thus it can be concluded as per the present study statistics that male employees showed more interest in participating in the survey. An age-wise distribution, the maximum number of employees, belonged to 38-47 age groups. It was seen that out of 400 respondents, most of the employees were post-graduate. When the employees' tenure period was recorded, it was found that the maximum percentage of respondents were working there for 8-11 years.

Figure 2. Graphical analysis of Demographic variables

4.2. Exploratory Factor Analysis and Scale Reliability

According to Nunnally (1978) Cronbach's alpha coefficient test is used to test the internal construct reliability thus the overall reliability for the scale exceeded the acceptable cut-off value of 0.70. To perform exploratory factor analysis, and support the dimensionality and convergent validity, KMO and Bartlett's test of sphericity with varimax rotation was run. As a result, factor analysis could be used to simplify or reduce data. Table 1 shows the factor loadings for each variable. Factor loadings were greater than 0.50, suggesting a satisfactory level of validity (Barclay, 1995).

Reliability test was undertaken to determine the internal consistency of the items that constituted each of the dimensions of HRMP. For an item to retain in the scale, it should have a minimum factor loading threshold of 0.5 (Hair et. al., 2006). All the 40 items were retained after the reliability test (see table 1). All the variables were also employed for further analyses as they all scored high Cronbach Alpha values, with .802 being the lowest score registered by employee performance, and .892 is the highest Cronbach Alpha score. A scale reliability test was also conducted to assess the internal consistency of the overall scale.

Table 1: Factor loads and Cronbach's Alpha for all variables.

Scale Items	Factor loads	Cronbach's Alpha
Organizational Culture		0.834
OC1	.615	
OC2	.682	
OC3	.790	
OC4	.705	
OC5	.710	
OC6	.635	
OC7	.676	

Selection & Recruitment		0.832
SR1	.710	
SR2	.723	
SR3	.653	
Training & Development		0.878
TD1	.725	
TD2	.694	
TD3	.610	
TD4	.774	
TD5	.735	
Rewards & Compensation		0.810
RC1	.605	
RC2	.682	
RC3	.690	
RC4	.668	
RC5	.720	
RC6	.745	
RC7	.736	
RC8	.688	
RC9	.705	
Performance Appraisal		0.866
PA1	.615	
PA2	.686	
PA3	.809	
PA4	.692	
PA5	.705	
PA6	.636	
Career Growth		0.856
CG1	.648	
CG2	.781	
CG3	.631	
Employee Communication		0.892
EC1	.728	
EC2	.735	
EC3	.715	
Employee Performance		0.802
EP1	.756	
EP2	.745	
EP3	.780	
EP4	.689	

4.3. Correlation Analysis Results

Before testing the mediating role of organizational culture in the relationship between predictors and outcomes, the correlation between independent and dependent variables and mediating variables were tested. The Pearson correlation statistical coefficient was used to verify the relationship between HRMP dimensions (SR, TD, C, PA, CG and EC) and EP before doing hierarchical regression analysis. The correlation coefficient between all variables was positive. Pearson correlation coefficient indicates the significance, direction, strength and significance of the bivariate relationship among all the variables measured at an interval or ratio level (Sekaran & Bougie, 2010). It is a statistical measure of association between two

variables. The positive correlation coefficient (r) ranges from ± 0.41 to ± 0.60 , while a strong correlation should be ± 0.61 to ± 0.80 . According to table 2, there is a positive correlation between human resources dimensions such as SR ($r = 0.656, p < 0.01$), TD ($r = 0.616, p < 0.01$), C is ($r = 0.717, p < 0.01$), PA ($r = 0.733, p < 0.01$), CG($r = 0.691, p < 0.01$) and EC($r = 0.677, p < 0.01$) with employee performance. Moreover OC ($r = 0.766, p < 0.01$) was found to be positively correlated with employee performance.

Table 2: Pearson Correlation Table.

Variables	SR	TD	C	PA	CG	EC	OC	EP
(SR)	1							
(TD)	.615**	1						
(C)	.575**	.777**	1					
(PA)	.572**	.753**	.794**	1				
(CG)	.509**	.709**	.729**	.832**	1			
(EC)	.541**	.655**	.651**	.653**	.730**	1		
(OC)	.838**	.835**	.742**	.745**	.691**	.654**	1	
(EP)	.656**	.616**	.717**	.733**	.691**	.677**	.766**	1

4.4. Hypothesis Testing

Regression was performed as shown in Table 3 to estimate the effect of HRMP dimensions (SR, TD, C, PA, CG and EC) on EP and examine the relationship between HRMP and EP in the Lebanese four and five stars hotels.

Table 3: Regression Analyses Results.

Hypothesized Relationships	Regression weights	T-values	Sig.	R Square	Supported/Not supported
H1 SR → Employee Performance	0.656	14.604	.000	.431	Supported
H2 TD → Employee Performance	0.616	13.137	.000	.380	Supported
H3 C → Employee Performance	0.717	17.249	.000	.513	Supported
H4 PA → Employee Performance	0.733	18.088	.000	.537	Supported
H5 CG → Employee Performance	0.691	16.056	.000	.478	Supported
H6 EC → Employee Performance	0.677	15.462	.000	.459	Supported

Mediating effect of OC between SR and EP -

H7A SR → OC → EP	0.767	.000	.588	Supported
<i>Mediating effect of OC between TD - and EP</i>				
H7B TD → OC → EP	0.768	.000	.589	Supported
<i>Mediating effect of OC between PRC - and EP</i>				
H7C C → OC → EP	0.798	.000	.636	Supported
<i>Mediating effect of OC between PA - and EP</i>				
H7D PA → OC → EP	0.804	.000	.646	Supported
<i>Mediating effect of OC between CG - and EP</i>				
H7E CG → OC → EP	0.798	.000	.637	Supported
<i>Mediating effect of OC between EC - and EP</i>				
H7F EC → OC → EP	0.801	.000	.641	Supported

Selection and recruitment are considered one of the most crucial and pivotal factors related to employee performance in the hotel sector. Table 3 showed that selection and recruitment SR was significantly related to the DV employee performance EP ($\beta = 0.584$, Sig. 0.000). Thus H1 was accepted. Besides, the value of R-Square increased from 0.431, thus demonstrating the relationship between SR and EP. The p-value of 0.000 is lower than the alpha-value 0.01. As a result, the descriptors used in this study's model are appropriate for identifying the change or variance between the variable and the dependent variables. In line with this finding, hypothesis H1 was supported. Similarly to these results, another study showed a significant linkage between SR and EP (Gamage, 2014; István, 2010; Sinha & Thaly, 2013).

Findings regarding TD, as shown in table 3 ($\beta=.616$, Sig. = .000), revealed a positive relationship between TD and EP. Thus H2 was accepted. R-Square's value is 0.380, and the p-value 0.000 is lower than 0.01 as an indicator of significance. As a result, the descriptors used in this study's model are appropriate to identify the relationship between the predictor variables and the dependent variables; thus, hypothesis H2 was supported. This result is consistent with (Yang & Fu, 2009; Karatepe et al., 2007; Dessler, 2008), who found a positive relationship between training and development and EP.

The same results were shown in table 3 regarding C, as shown in table 5 ($\beta=.717$, Sig. = .000) revealed that there is a positive relationship between C and EP. Thus H3 was accepted. R-Square's value is 0.513, and the p-value 0.000 is lower than 0.01 as an indicator of significance. As a result, the descriptors used in this study's model are appropriate to identify the relationship between the predictor variables and the dependent variables; thus, hypothesis H3 was supported. This result is consistent with Teseema and Soeters (2006), who found a positive relationship between compensation and EP.

Findings regarding PA, as shown in table 3 ($\beta=.733$, Sig. = .000), revealed a positive relationship between PA and EP. Thus H4 was accepted. R-Square's value is 0.537, and the p-value 0.000 is lower than 0.01 as an indicator of significance. As a result, the descriptors used

in this study's model are appropriate to identify the relationship between the predictor variables and the dependent variables; thus, hypothesis H4 was supported. This result is consistent with Sels et al. (2003), who found a positive relationship between performance appraisal and EP.

Moreover, table 3 shows a significant relationship between CG and EP ($\beta=.691$, Sig. = .000). Thus H5 was accepted. The value of R-Square is 0.478. In line with these findings, H5 was supported. Many researchers previously presented similar results (Akmal, 2015; Dewi & Utama, 2016; Charity, 2015) proved that career growth was significantly related to employee performance

Findings regarding EC, as shown in table 3 ($\beta=.677$, Sig. = .000), revealed a positive relationship between EC and EP. Thus H6 was accepted. R-Square's value is 0.459, and the p-value 0.000 is lower than 0.01 as an indicator of significance. As a result, the descriptors used in this study's model are appropriate to identify the relationship between the predictor variables and the dependent variables; hence hypothesis H6 was supported. This result is consistent with Salako (2016), who found a positive relationship between employee communication and EP.

Finally, table 3 also support and prove the indirect effects results that there is a mediating relationship between HRMP (SR, TD, C, PA, CG, and EC) as independent variables, OC as mediating variable and EP as a dependent variable through the below hypotheses hierarchical regression results H7A R-Square .588, H7B R-Square .589, H7C R-Square .636, H7D R-Square .646, H7E R-Square .637 and H7F R-Square .641.

5. Conclusions, Implications and Limitations

The main question brought to the attention of the HRM researcher communities is to relate a pattern of complementary effects between HR practices, organisational culture and employee performance (Setyawaty et al., 2017; Walumbwa et al., 2011; Zehir, 2010). This study offers a theoretical framework and empirical analysis that contributes to advancing our understanding of these effects. Our findings suggest that HR practices have a unique relationship with employee performance. Simultaneously, the apparent use of influential organisational culture leads to enhanced job performance. Therefore, our findings support the research model indicating that HR practices motivate employees to improve their in-role performances and that opportunity-enhancing HR practices offer employees various opportunities to contribute and accomplish their in-role performance.

In addition to these, our results support the effectiveness of examining the mediating role of organisational culture. In particular, our results indicate that while HR practices impact the employee performance, the organisational culture boosts this relationship; therefore, employees who adjust well and experience high levels of social well-being are likely to experience a sense of importance that enables them to accomplish both their in-role and innovative job performance. Finally, that culture encourages employees to persevere when facing the challenges inherent in creative and innovative work, enhancing their innovative job performance. Consequently, employees return this organisational investment in the form of increased performance.

From a practical viewpoint, our results suggest that organisations can acquire extensive (but diverse) benefits when investing in different HR practices. Our study also revealed that motivation-enhancing HR practices enhance organisational culture, which increases innovative job performance by employees. Hence, when organisations need to improve employees' psychological condition and encourage them to be more creative and innovative, they should significantly invest in accurate and fair compensation, as well as provide them with meaningful and stimulating tasks. Additionally, to encourage innovative behaviour among employees, organisations should make an effort to establish long-term employment relationships. Therefore, when organisations aim to improve employees' health-related

conditions and employee relationships with peers, organisations should focus more on practices, such as training and development, and involve employees in teamwork. Furthermore, to reduce stress and work intensification among employees and boost their in-role performances, it is advised that organisations instruct employees on how to complete their work effectively and encourage their decision-making involvement. Hence, organisations should use appropriate HR practices dimensions to maximise the return on their investment in HRM.

Our study is not without limitations. The HRM data were based on employee insights and examined HR practices' perceived use. Future research should consider investigating the actual use of HR practices in the hotel sector. The study's design is similar to other HRM studies reporting meaningful relationship between variables (Setyawaty et al., 2017); future studies should examine the mediation processes using different data. The study did not have a multilevel design, and the findings should be interpreted with this limitation in mind.

Additionally, the high employee performance might result from the excellent reputation of the case company, its corporate policy, and its relatively higher salaries than other similar companies in the sector, but not a consequence of using different dimensions of HR practices corporate culture. Hence, the study results may not be fully generalizable to other organisations. However, this might also explain the stronger than average Cronbach's α of the study's core constructs. Future research should also study the examined associations in other industry and sector settings.

Overall, the study illustrates that even though the different dimension of HR practices can enhance different proportions of organisational culture, which, in turn, increase different types of employee performance, these HR practices work the same way and do not seem to generate any unplanned consequences or trade-offs in terms of reduced employee physical well-being. Thus, our study highlights a series of essential pathways for organisational culture and employee performance. The study will initiate more theoretical and empirical research on how to make employees happy, healthy and social, thus generating employee performance synergies.

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Ghanem, A. and Ozgit, H.

2021, Vol.6, No.2, pp. 867-889. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6479188

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